

Studies on 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions[†]

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1,3-Dipolar species are 4π -electron systems which can undergo facile concerted ($\pi^A s + \pi^2 s$) cycloadditions to double and triple bonds. 1,3-Dipolar species can be divided into two categories : (i) those of the propargyl – allenic type, where the central atom is sp -hybridised, and (ii) those which are isoelectronic with allyl anions, where the central atom is sp^2 -hybridised. In valence-bond terms the electronic structures of the 1,3-dipolar species are represented as resonance hybrids of canonical forms which involve charge-separation. It must be remembered, however, that these are not zwitterionic species with separate positive and negative charges. Rather, the four π -electrons are delocalised over three atomic centres with greater electron-density on the terminal atoms particularly on the more electronegative heteroatom if the terminal atoms are different. Representative members of 1,3-dipolar species are shown in Chart 1¹⁻³.

the addition of nitrones to olefins was discovered independently by Cope, LeBel, Brown, Delpierre and Huisgen. Nitrones undergo facile concerted ($\pi^A s + \pi^2 s$) cycloadditions to olefins and acetylenes to yield isoxazolidine and isoxazoline derivatives¹⁻⁷. These reduced isoxazole derivatives can be used as templates to generate several types of 1,3-difunctionalised compounds, which can serve as key synthetic intermediates. As considerable regiochemical and stereochemical control can be exerted in the cycloaddition step by choosing appropriate substituents on the dipole and the dipolarophile, nitrono cycloadditions constitute an important synthetic route to 1,3-difunctionalised compounds. Regioselectively of the cycloaddition to generate 4- or 5-substituted isoxazolidine/isoxazoline derivatives from mono-substituted olefins and acetylenes depend on the nature of the substituent. Extensive work has been described

Chart 1. Classification of 1,3-dipolar species.

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions to multiple bonds constitute a major synthetic technique for the construction of 5-membered heterocyclic rings. Nitrones are an important class of 1,3-dipolar species. These were discovered by E. Beckmann in the 1880s by the *N*-alkylation of oximes. In the 1960s,

on mono-substituted olefins and acetylenes⁴⁻⁷. Some representative examples are given in Table 1⁶. These studies revealed that with most substituents the 5-substituted heterocycle was formed preferentially. However, strongly electron-withdrawing substituents on the dipolarophile change the

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Table 1. Regioselectivity in nitrono cycloaddition reactions*

Olefins	Nitrones	Ratio of 5 : 4 substitution
Ph-CH=CH ₂	<i>C,N</i> -Diphenyl	~100 : 0
CH ₃ O ₂ C-CH=CH ₂	<i>C,N</i> -Diphenyl	100 : 0
AcO-CH=CH ₂	<i>C,N</i> -Diphenyl	~100 : 0
PhSO ₂ -CH=CH ₂	<i>C</i> -Phenyl, <i>N</i> -methyl	32 : 68
CH ₃ O ₂ C-C≡CH	<i>C</i> -Phenyl, <i>N</i> -methyl	42 : 52
(<i>E</i>)-CH ₃ -CH=CH-CO ₂ CH ₃	<i>C,N</i> -Diphenyl	~0 : 100 ^a
(<i>E</i>)-Ph-CH=CH-NO ₂	<i>C</i> -Benzoyl, <i>N</i> -phenyl	~0 : 100 ^b

*As reported previously in the literatur⁶. ^a4-CO₂CH₃; ^b4-NO₂.

selectivity to favour the formation of the 4-substituted heterocycles. Stereoselectivity seems to be affected by both electronic and steric demands, and is often very delicately balanced. Disubstituted olefins were studied earlier to a much lesser extent.

Our investigations have been focussed on nitrono cycloadditions of 1,2-disubstituted olefins in which the double bond is conjugated with a carbonyl group. The types of reactions investigated so far include cycloadditions of (i) *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones to substituted cinnamic acid piperidides, (ii) *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones to substituted cinnamic acid piperidides, (iii) *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones to 5-aryl-2*E*,5*E*-pentadienamides, (iv) *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones to butenolide, (v) cyclic nitrones, viz. 1 pyrroline 1-oxide and 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine 1-oxide to substituted cinnamic acid piperidides. These reactions have been thoroughly investigated with respect to their regio- and stereoselectivities. Structure elucidations and determination of conformational preferences were achieved by detailed spectroscopic (essentially NMR) studies and also by X-ray crystallographic analyses. Attempts have been made to rationalise the results in terms of FMO interactions and steric factors. Conformational analyses utilising NMR studies and Molecular Mechanics calculations have been carried out.

Nitrones can be generated⁸ by the following methods : (i) *N*-alkylation of oximes, (ii) condensation of aldehydes and ketones with *N*-substituted hydroxylamines, (iii) oxidation of nitrogen heterocycles.

We have prepared the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones in the usual way by warming the appropriate aldehydes with *N*-phenylhydroxylamine in ethanol, and then keeping the reaction mixtures overnight to obtain the crystalline nitrones. Aromatic aldehydes were reacted with *N*-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium hydrogen carbonate in refluxing methylene chloride for a few hours to obtain *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones as in previous literature reports. We have found recently that the reaction times between the carbonyl compounds and phenylhydroxylamine and methylhydroxylamine can be reduced to the order of minutes by using microwave irradiation techniques⁹. Five- and six-membered nitrones have been obtained by the established method of selenium dioxide catalysed oxidation of pyrrolidine or piperidine with hydrogen peroxide¹⁰.

Cycloadditions to 2-butenolide

The cycloadditions of the four *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones (1-4) to the conjugated lactone 2-butenolide (5) were investigated in our first series of experiments¹¹. Two diastereoisomeric tetrahydrofuro[3,4-*d*]isoxazole derived bicyclic cycloadducts, and a ring-opened butenolide (derived from the major cycloadduct) were obtained (Chart 2). Previous to our work, there was only one report on nitrono cycloadditions to conjugated lactones¹². Our work also opened a new synthetic route to enrich the family of the comparatively rare biheterocycle furo[3,4-*d*]isoxazoles, the first member of

Chart 2. Cycloaddition of *C*, *N*-diarylnitrones to 2-butenolide. Synthesis of 2,3,6,6a-tetrahydrofuro[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-(3*aH*)one.

which was synthesised by Quilico *et al.*¹³.

These cycloadditions were performed in refluxing toluene (or in a sealed tube at 110–115°) for 12 h. The 3*RS*-(3*R**, 3*aR**, 6*aS**)-2,3,6,6*a*-tetrahydrofuro[3,4-*d*]isoxazole cycloadducts (**6a-d**) (the all-*cis* isomer; isolated yields 25–30%) predominated over the corresponding 3*RS*-(3*R**, 3*aS**, 6*aR**) cycloadducts (**7a-d**) (3,3*a*-*trans* isomer; isolated yields 20–25%). Butanolide derivatives obtained by ring-opening of the major cycloadduct constituted the third product (**8a-c**) isolated in 15–20% yields. The chemical shifts and coupling pattern (as apparent from the ¹H-¹H-decoupling experiments) decided in favour of the 2,3,6,6*a*-tetrahydrofuro[3,4-*d*]isoxazol-4(3*aH*)one structures instead of the regioisomeric 2,3,3*a*,4-tetrahydrofuro[4,3-*d*]isoxazol-6(6*aH*)-one structures for the cycloadducts. The 300 MHz ¹H NMR and 75.5 MHz ¹³C NMR characteristics of the ring-protons and carbons for **6c**, **7c** and **8c** are given in Table 2.

Table 2. 300 MHz ¹H NMR^a and 75.5 MHz ¹³C NMR^b assignments of **6c**, **7c** and **8c**

Proton number	6c	7c	8c^d	Carbon number	6c	7c	8c^d
H-3	5.02 (d)	4.94 (d)	5.00 (d)	C-3	71.44	71.28	54.88
H-3 <i>a</i>	3.84 (dd)	3.48 (dd)	2.89 (t)	C-3 <i>a</i>	54.52	57.39	49.87
H-6 <i>a</i>	5.23 (m)	5.13 (m)	4.46 (m)	C-4	173.50	175.19	174.60
H _A -6	4.53 ^c	4.60 ^c	4.25 ^c	C-6	71.28	70.88	74.97
H _B -6	4.51 ^c	4.49 ^c	4.21 ^c	C-6 <i>a</i>	77.99	77.25	70.39
Coupling constants (Hz)							
<i>J</i> _{3,3<i>a</i>}	9.0	2.9	5.4				
<i>J</i> _{3<i>a</i>,6<i>a</i>}	7.7	6.5	4.8				
<i>J</i> _{6<i>a</i>,6-H/A}	2.0	–	–				
<i>J</i> _{6<i>a</i>,6-H/B}	6.2	4.6	2.8				
<i>J</i> _{6-H/A,6-H/B}	10.9	11.2	10.8				

^aCoupling constants and chemical shifts were calculated exactly by aid of the PANIC programme (see Fig. 1).

^bAssignments were made for compounds with the help of 1-bond and long-range 2D-correlations by the XHCORR-sequence (see Fig. 2).

^cSecond-order spectra – overlapped and complicated patterns.

^dNumbering of ring-opened product taken to follow those of cycloadducts.

The chemical shifts and coupling constants were precisely determined by computer – assisted calculations done by the Bruker software 'Parameter Adjustment in NMR by Iteration Calculations' (acronym – PANIC) (see Fig. 1). The relative configurations of the products were established from the magnitude of the coupling constant *J*_{3,3*a*}. The *cis*-isomers (**6a-d**) showed a larger coupling constant of about 9 Hz between H-3/H-3*a* while the *trans* – H-3/H-3*a* isomers (**7a-d**) showed a smaller *J*_{3,3*a*} of about 3 Hz. *J*_{3*a*,6*a*} was

Fig. 1 Simulated 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum of the non-aromatic protons of **6** (R=NO₂) matching the experimental spectrum (<0.2 Hz difference in peak positions). Calculations done by Bruker programme PANIC.

7.5–8.2 Hz indicating the *cis*-orientation of these protons. ¹³C NMR assignments were made for the compounds with the aid of 1-bond and long-range 2D-correlations by the XHCORR-sequence (Fig. 2 for **6c**).

Fig. 2. 1-Bond heteronuclear shift correlation spectrum of **6** (R = NO₂) using XHCORR sequence.

It was established that the ring-opened products (**8a-c**) were derived from the *cis*-isomer. This transformation could be achieved by refluxing the *cis*-isomer (**6c**) in moist toluene for 12 h when it was partially converted to **8c**. Under these

conditions, the *trans*-product (7c) remained unchanged. The comparative lability of the *cis*-cycloadducts could be explained on the basis of greater non-bonded steric interactions present in the molecule, the reaction presumably occurring by a S_N2 displacement at C-6a. The dominant FMO interactions in these cycloadditions seem to be the dipole HOMO-dipolarophile LUMO (Sustmann Type I) for (1,2,4) – while both FMO interactions are probably comparable for the reaction with 3^{1,3,14,15}. For both types of interactions, pairing of the larger coefficients on the dipole and dipolarophile lead to the observed regioselectivity.

The total yield of the *cis*-isomer (including the ring-opened product) derived from the *exo*-approach was greater (~2 : 1 ratio) compared to the cycloadduct 7 derived from the *endo*-approach. The *exo*-geometry of approach has favourable secondary orbital interactions between the MOs of the *C*-aryl ring of the nitron and the carbonyl oxygen.

Cycloaddition of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones

Much of our efforts have been devoted to a detailed study of the cycloaddition of the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones (1-4) to differently substituted cinnamic acid piperidides (9-12)^{11b,16-19}. It is a known fact that the regiochemistry of cycloaddition is dictated by the nature of the substituent attached to the multiple bond of the dipolarophile (Table 1). It had been earlier reported that both propylene and styrene reacted with *C,N*-diphenylnitron to give 5-substituted isoxazolidines⁶. Similarly, methyl acrylate gave diastereoisomeric 5-substituted products (Table 1)⁶. Substitution at both ends of a double bond with an aryl group and a carbomethoxy group gave a preponderance of the product (13) in which the carbomethoxy group was at position-4⁶. We wanted to investigate the regiochemical outcome with 1,2-disubstituted olefins, where the substituents were an aryl group and a carbonyl group. Earlier reports on the effect on regioselectivities were observed by changing the substituent or functional group attached to the multiple bond. It was of interest to us to find out how sensitive were the cycloaddition regioselectivities to changes in aryl substituents on the dipole and the dipolarophile. It was satisfying to observe that in many cases the small perturbations caused by changes in the *para*-substituents did lead to some changes in regioselectivities. Changes in aryl substituents did not affect the *endo*-stereoselectivity of the cycloaddition process – this was of course to be expected.

The *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones (1-4) were reacted with differently substituted *N*-cinnamoylpiperidines (9-12) where the *para*-substituent groups varied from the strongly electron-withdrawing nitro- to the strongly electron-donating methoxyl (Chart 3). The reactions were carried out in re-

Chart 3. Cycloaddition of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones to *l*-cinnamoylpiperidines

fluxing toluene (110°) under nitrogen atmosphere. TLC and ¹H NMR monitoring of the reactants showed that usually periods of 30–40 h were necessary to obtain the products in good yields. At the end of this period, only small amounts of the dipolarophile survived. Reaction rates with *p*-nitro substituted dipoles and dipolarophiles were somewhat faster and less decomposition of the cycloadduct occurred. Much higher temperatures for the cycloadditions could not be used, as at these higher temperatures (i) the nitrones started decomposing or rearranging to amides, and (ii) the cycloadducts themselves started decomposing. Many of the reactions were monitored using ¹H NMR spectroscopy as the probe. It was found that the relative amounts of the regioisomeric and stereoisomeric products remained the same as the reaction proceeded; thus the relative proportions seemed to be the result of kinetic control – cycloreversion did not seem to occur to an appreciable extent under the reaction conditions. It was important from the viewpoint of stereoselectivity to know the configuration of the reacting *C,N*-diarylnitron. Literature reports indicated that these existed preferentially with the aryl groups *trans* to each other^{3,4,6}. This we could corroborate by ¹H NMR studies of the reacting nitron – before and during the reaction.

Product isolation was done by chromatography over neutral alumina of the post-reaction mixture, after the solvent

was stripped off under reduced pressure. Two products, the all-*trans* (3,4-*trans*, 4,5-*trans*) series (14) and the diastereoisomeric 3,4-*cis*, 4,5-*trans* series (15) of 5-aryl-4-piperidinyloxisoxazolidines could be isolated in all the reactions. The regioisomeric all-*trans* (3,4-*trans*, 4,5-*trans*) 4-aryl-5-piperidinyloxisoxazolidines (16) were also obtained in certain reactions, where electron-withdrawing groups were present on the aryl rings of the dipolarophile or the nitron. Occasionally a ring-opened product, derived from a cycloadduct was obtained; these products have been tentatively formulated as 17. The structure and stereochemistry of the products were established on the basis of spectroscopic data, particularly NMR and X-ray crystallographic analyses. The 300 MHz ^1H NMR and 75.5 MHz ^{13}C NMR assignments of representative compounds are collected in Table 3. Assignments were confirmed for representative examples by ^1H - ^1H -COSY, ^1H - ^{13}C -COSY-LR and C-H

correlations by the XHCORR sequence (with parameters optimised for both one-bond and long-range C-H couplings) and by spectrum – simulations using the Bruker software PANIC.

In the product series 14 and 15, the benzylic protons (H-3 and H-5) appeared as doublets, the signal positions being significantly downfield of the signal of the protons attached to C-4, which also bore the piperidinyloxo group. The H-5 signal moved upfield by about 0.7 ppm, and the H-4 signal moved about 1 ppm downfield in the regioisomeric 16 when compared to 14. H-3 and H-5 in 14 and 15 showed long-range coupling in their COSY-LR spectra with *ortho*-protons of the attached aromatic rings (see for example, Fig. 3 for 14 : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{NO}_2$ while the COSY-

Table 3. 300 MHz ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR assignments of 14 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{Cl}$) and 15 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{Cl}$)

Carbon/ ¹ H NMR of	^{13}C NMR of	^1H NMR of	^{13}C NMR of
proton	14 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{Cl}$)	14 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{Cl}$)	15 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{Cl}$)
3	5.48; d 8	74.87	5.98; d 9.2
4	3.73; dd 8, 9.4	62.74	3.79; dd 9.2, 10.6
5	5.30; d 9.4	84.22	4.91; d 10.2
D-2	3.49; m 3.60; m	43.90	3.49; m
D-3 } D-4 } D-5 }	1.41; m 0.76; m 0.96; m	25.70 24.07 26.30	1.3–1.6; m
D-6	2.72; m	46.90	3.10; m 2.82; m
C=O	–	165.66	–
A-1	–	151.39	–
A-2,6 } A-4 }	6.97; m	114.09 122.27	6.94; d 7.9 6.99; t 7.4
A-3, 5	7.27; t 8.0	129.11	7.23; t 7.7
B-1	–	147.58	–
B-2, 6 } B-3, 5 }	7.73; d 8.4 8.27; d 8.4	127.93 124.37	7.71; d 8.6 8.25; d 8.6
B-4	–	147.60	–
C-1	–	134.96	–
C-2, 6 } C-3, 5 }	7.40; m	127.00 127.93	7.45; d 8.5 7.37; d 8.5
C-4	–	134.15	–

*Chemical shifts in δ , ppm; J in Hz. Aryl rings : A : attached to N-2; B : attached to C-3; C : attached to C-5; D : piperidine ring.

Fig. 3. 300 MHz ^1H - ^1H -COSY-LR spectrum of 14 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{NO}_2$) showing long-range correlations between H-3 and H-5 with *ortho*-aromatic protons.

LR spectrum of 16 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{NO}_2$) showed long-range ^1H - ^1H couplings between H-3 and H-4 with *ortho*-aromatic protons (Fig. 4). Fig. 5 shows the heteronuclear shift correlation spectrum (XHCORR) of 14 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{NO}_2$) with parameters optimised for small long-range ^{13}C - ^1H couplings – this showed LR-couplings between H-3 and H-5 with the corresponding *ortho*-carbons in aromatic rings

Fig. 4 300 MHz $^1\text{H}-^1\text{H}$ -COSY-LR spectrum of 16 ($\text{R}^1=\text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{NO}_2$) showing long-range correlations between H-3 and H-4 with *ortho*-aromatic protons

Fig. 5 Heteronuclear shift correlation spectrum of 14 ($\text{R}^1=\text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{NO}_2$) – parameters optimised for long-range couplings

B and C. The mass spectral fragmentations of 14 and 15 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{NO}_2$) showed two fragments at m/z 340 and

151 by 4,5-bond cleavage, while in compound 16 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{Cl}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{NO}_2$) similar fragmentation resulted in peaks at m/z 350 and 141. All the above observations decided unambiguously that while product series 14 and 15 were diastereoisomeric possessing structures with a 4-piperidinyl-oxo-5-aryl system, product series 16 was regioisomeric having a 4-aryl-5-piperidinyl-oxo system.

Since the magnitude of the coupling constants in 5-membered rings do not always lend themselves to stereochemical assignments, recourse was taken to X-ray crystallographic analyses. The X-ray analysis of 14 ($\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{Cl}$) showed the compound to have the all-*trans* stereochemistry – 3,4-*trans*-4,5-*trans*, as well as the N2 lone-pair *trans* to C3-H. Compound 14 crystallised in the triclinic system in the space group P_1 (Fig. 6)^{16 17}. X-Ray crystallographic analyses were also done with representative members of the series 15 and 16¹⁷.

Fig. 6 X-Ray crystallographic structure of 14 ($\text{R}^1=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Cl}$) and conformations 14 ($\text{R}^1=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Cl}$) and 15 ($\text{R}^1=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^2=\text{Cl}$) as calculated by DISCOVERY module of Insight-II Molecular Modelling package (MSI Inc) on Silicon Graphics Indigo 2 workstation

Calculations on energy minimization of the regio- and stereoisomeric cycloadducts were done by taking advantage of the X-ray crystallographic data of the cycloadducts¹⁷. Energy minimization has been achieved by conjugate gradient

method using the DISCOVER module of Insight-II molecular modeling package (MSI Inc) running on a Silicon Graphics Indigo 2 workstation. In conformational analysis the total energy is the sum of the kinetic and potential energies. This potential energy function consists of the following terms as given in the following equation :

$$\begin{aligned}
 v(r) = & v(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{N_{at}}) \\
 (\text{P.E.}) & \sum_{n=1}^{N_b} \frac{1}{2} K_{bn} (b_n - b_{on})^2 + \sum_{n=1}^{N_\theta} \frac{1}{2} K_{\theta n} (\theta_n - \theta_{en})^2 \\
 & \quad \text{Bonds} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{Angle} \\
 & + \sum_{n=1}^{N_\xi} \frac{1}{2} K_{\xi n} (\xi_n - \xi_{on})^2 + \sum_{n=1}^{N_\phi} \frac{1}{2} K_{\phi} [1 + \epsilon \cos(n\phi_n - \delta_n)] \\
 & \quad \text{improper torsion} \qquad \qquad \text{electrostatic} \\
 & + \sum_{i < j}^{N_{at}} [A/r^{12}{}_{ij} - C_{ij}/r^6_{ij} + q_i q_j / (4\pi\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r r_{ij})] \\
 & \quad \text{van der Waals} \qquad \text{electrostatic} \\
 & + \text{others} \qquad \qquad \qquad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{N_{at}}$ represent the coordinates of the system that is being investigated. Non-bonded interactions are effectively supplied by the last three terms in eqn. (1).

The results revealed that the most stable conformer of the major all-*trans* cycloadduct (**14**; $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{Cl}$) had 3.9 kcal mol⁻¹ less than the most stable conformer of the corresponding 3,4-*cis*-4,5-*trans*-cycloadduct (**15**; $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{Cl}$) (Fig. 6)¹⁷.

The proportions of the cycloadducts in the crude product mixture was determined by ¹H NMR. This was found to be 100 : 12–15 for the all-*trans* (**14**) : 3,4-*cis*-4,5-*trans* (**15**) isomers. The diastereoisomeric excess (*de*) was thus ~76–84%. Some results are collected in Table 4. In some of

Table 4. Relative proportions of products obtained on cycloaddition of *C*-aryl, *N*-phenyl nitrones to *N*-cinnamoylpiperidines

Substituents	3,4- <i>trans</i> -4,5- <i>trans</i> Isomer (major product) (14)	3,4- <i>cis</i> -4,5- <i>trans</i> Isomer (minor product) (15)	3,4- <i>trans</i> -4,5- <i>trans</i> Regioisomer (16)
$R^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $R^2 = \text{Cl}$	100	9	10
$R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{H}$	100	8	–
$R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{Cl}$	100	10	5
$R^1 = \text{Cl}$, $R^2 = \text{H}$	100	11	–
$R^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $R^2 = \text{H}$	100	9	13

the reactions, particularly where the strongly electron-withdrawing nitro group was present in the aryl nucleus of the dipolarophile and the dipole, the regioisomer (**16**) was also formed.

The regio- and stereochemical courses of cycloadditions could be rationalised on the basis of FMO theory. Mention may be made in this connection of the earlier work of Jouçla *et al.*²⁰ Sustmann¹⁴ classified 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions into three types, the predominant type of HOMO-LUMO interaction depending on the substituents on the dipole and dipolarophile : Type I - Dipole - HOMO controlled, Type II - Both pairs of FMO interactions are important, and Type III - Dipole - LUMO controlled.

The formation of that regioisomer would be favoured in which the larger terminal coefficients interact. Qualitatively, the HOMOs and LUMOs of all the diarylnitrones have similar shapes with $C_{O-3} > C_{C-1}$ in the HOMO and $C_{O-3} < C_{C-1}$ in the LUMO (Table 5)²⁰. For these aldonitrones, both the interactions, viz. dipole-HOMO controlled and dipole-

Table 5. F.M.O. energies and atomic orbital coefficients of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones

Compd. no.	R	M.O. energy in eV		A.O. coefficient		
		HOMO	LUMO	C(1)	N(2)	O(3)
1	H^a	HO	-9.60	-0.46	-0.25	0.67
		LU	2.06	0.44	-0.42	0.25
4	OCH_3^a	HO	-9.20	-0.40	-0.27	0.61
		LU	2.19	0.44	-0.41	0.25
3	NO_2^a	HO	-10.25	-0.48	-0.24	0.67
		LU	1.07	0.34	-0.41	0.25
1	H^b	HO	-8.38	-0.43	-0.25	0.55
		LU	-1.09	0.44	-0.34	0.27

^aCalculated by CNDO method.

^bCalculated by MINDO method²⁰.

LUMO controlled, would favour the formation of the same regioisomeric transition state which would lead to 2,3,5-triaryl-4-piperidinyloxisoxazolidine (Chart 4). The pres-

Chart 4. Regiocontrol of cycloaddition reaction of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones.

ence of an electron-withdrawing group such as *p*-nitro in the dipolarophile would lower HOMO and LUMO energies and reduce the difference in magnitude between the orbital coefficients on C-2 and C-3 – hence reactions involving **11** as the dipolarophile are expected to be less regioselective. Presence of a *p*-chloro-substituent as in **10** would also be expected to reduce regioselectivity, albeit to a lesser extent. The differentiation in the magnitude of the coefficients in the LUMO of the *N*-phenyl-*C*-(4-nitrophenyl)nitron (3) is less than in the others – this would lead to a loss of regioselectivity in reactions of **3**. The observed results were in accord with these expectations.

A high degree of stereoselectivity was observed in these reactions. *C,N*-Diaryl nitrones react in the *E*-form. The *endo*-mode of approach, leading to the all-*trans* isomer, is expected to predominate due to favourable secondary orbital interactions for both the regioisomeric transition states. These predictions are in accord with the observed diastereoselectivities (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Stereocontrol of the cycloaddition of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl to *N*-cinnamoylpiperidines.

A similar series of cycloaddition reactions have been carried out with *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones (**18-21**) with differently substituted cinnamic acid piperidides^{19,21}. The results were similar – the all-*trans*-2-methyl-3,5-triaryl-4-piperidinyloxoisoxazolidine cycloadducts (**22**) were the major products, with the diastereoisomeric 3,6-*cis*-4,5-*trans* cycloadducts (**23**) being the minor products (Chart 5). NMR and X-ray crystallographic studies of the cycloadducts confirmed the structural and stereochemical assignments.

Another series of investigations involved reactions between equimolar proportions of 5-aryl-2*E*,4*E*-dienamides, e.g. **24**, and *C*-phenyl-*N*-arylnitrones (**1-4**). The nitrone was added slowly over a period of hours to the reaction mixture to keep an excess of the dipolarophile at all times. This way the formation of *bis*-adducts were suppressed. It was found that the reaction occurred preferentially at the more reactive α,β -conjugated double bond to give products **25** and **26**^{19,22}, the former predominating (Chart 6).

Chart 5. Cycloaddition of *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones to cinnamic acid piperidides.

Chart 6. Cycloaddition of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylalidonitrones to 1,4-disubstituted-1,3-diene compounds

Cycloadditions of 1-pyrroline 1-oxide

Our attention was next turned to the cycloaddition reactions of cyclic nitrones. The cycloaddition of the five-membered cyclic nitrone 1-pyrroline 1-oxide (**27**) to 1-cinnamoylpiperidine (**9**) and its aryl-substituted derivatives (**10**, **11**) were studied²³. The cycloadditions were performed by refluxing equimolar amounts of the dipoles and dipolarophiles in anhydrous toluene for several hours under nitrogen atmosphere – the post-reaction mixture on chromatography over silica-gel yielded two regioisomeric cycloadducts, 2-aryl-3-piperidinyloxo-2,3,3*a*,4,5,6-hexahydropyrrolo[1,2-*b*]isoxazole (**28**) and 3-aryl-2-piperi-

dinyloxo-2,3,3a,4,5,6-hexahydropyrrolo[1,2-*b*]isoxazole (29) (Chart 7).

Chart 7. Cycloaddition of 1-pyrroline-1-oxide to 1-cinnamoylpiperidine and its derivatives.

The regioisomeric cycloadducts could be distinguished from their ^1H NMR characteristics. The low-field H-2 doublet appeared at δ 4.62 in **29** (R = H), nearly 1 ppm upfield when compared to the H-2 doublet (δ 5.52) in **28** (R = H). On the other hand, the H-3 signal of **29** (R = H) appeared at δ 3.99 as a double doublet, nearly 0.5 ppm downfield of the corresponding signal in **28** (R = H). It is known that in simple systems of the type Ph-CH<, the methine proton appears at δ 2.8–2.9, while the methine signal position in compounds of the type –CHCONR₂ is $\sim\delta$ 2.2, an upfield shift of \sim 0.6–0.7 ppm. Keeping these data in mind, we could assign structures **28** (R = H, Cl, NO₂) to the 2-aryl-3-carboxamido series and structures **29** (R = H, Cl, NO₂) to the 2-carboxamido-3-aryl series of cycloadducts. The proposed regiochemistry of the two series of cycloadducts were confirmed by COSY-LR analysis of the cycloadducts (Figs. 8 and 9). H-2 showed long-range correlation with the aromatic *ortho*-protons at δ 7.48 in **28** (R = H) (Fig. 8), whereas similar long-range correlation of H-3 with aromatic *ortho*-protons was observed for **29** (R = H) (Fig. 9). The ^{13}C NMR data of the two series of cycloadducts were broadly similar with slight variations reflective of their regioisomeric relationship.

The mass-spectral fragmentation patterns of **28** (R = H) and **29** (R = H) were similar in some respects, which reflected the general similarity in their structures; for example, both compounds gave fragments at m/z 215 and 86 arising from electron-impact induced cycloreversion. However, the EI-MS of **28** (R = H) showed two fragments at m/z 194 and 106, whereas similar fragmentation of **29** (R = H) in its CI-

Fig. 8. 300 MHz ^1H - ^1H -COSY-LR spectrum of **28** (R=H) showing long-range correlations between H-2 with *ortho*-aromatic protons.

MS gave two peaks at m/z 159 and 142. This was reflective of the regioisomeric nature of the two types of cycloadducts (Chart 8). The relative configuration of **28** (R = H) was established by X-ray crystallographic analysis. This estab-

Chart 8. MS fragmentation pattern of **28** and **29**.

Fig. 9 300 MHz ^1H - ^1H -COSY-LR spectrum 29 (R=H) showing long-range correlations between H-3 with *ortho*-aromatic protons

lished it to be the 3-3*a* *cis*-isomer (Fig. 10). The A-B ring juncture is *cis*-with the lone-pair of the tertiary nitrogen pointing in the same direction as the C_(3*a*)-H bond with the N-atom clearly pyramidal. The J_{3-3a} values for the pair of regioisomers were similar, indicating that they had the same relative stereochemistry at the 3-3*a* position; thus series 29 of cycloadducts were also assigned the *cis*-3-3*a* stereochem-

Fig. 10 X-Ray crystallographic structure of 5-5-cycloadduct 28 (3-3*a* *cis*-isomer)

istry. The *cis*-3-3*a*-isomers of both the series were formed by *endo*-approach in either case due to favourable secondary-orbital interactions (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11 Stereocontrol of the cycloadditions of Δ^1 -pyrroline-1-oxide to *N*-cinnamoylpiperidines

Cycloadditions of 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-1-oxide

The next series of cycloadditions that we investigated were those of the 6-membered cyclic nitron 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-1-oxide (30)²⁴, with the dipolarophiles (9-11). Selectivities were lower; all the four possible types of cycloadducts (31-34) could be isolated for these reactions (Chart 9). Similar results were obtained for cycloadditions of 3,4-dehydro-morpholine-4-oxide²⁵. Two series of cycloadducts, viz. 31 and 32 showed considerable conformational mobility, in so far as two rapidly interconvertible conformers were present in solution at ambient temperatures. The ^1H NMR spectrum of 31 (R = H) showed two sets of signals of protons at or near the ring juncture (i.e. H-

Chart 9 Cycloaddition of 3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine-1-oxide to cinnamic acid piperidines

6-cyano-2-oxo-8-phenyl-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octane (**43**) derived from cycloadduct **40**. The *exo*-**40** and *endo*-**41** adducts could be distinguished from the coupling pattern of H-5 for the *exo*-adduct (**40**) this signal appeared as a doublet at δ 4.96 ($J_{4,5}$ 4.8 Hz) showing the absence of a coupling between H-5 and H-6 (ϕ H-C₅-C₆-H \sim 90°) at δ 4.94 showing appreciable coupling between H-5 and H-6 (ϕ H-C₅-C₆-H \sim 30°). ¹H-¹H-decoupling experiments and a COSY-45° 2D-experiment established the regioisomeric nature of cycloadduct **42**. The formation of **40** and **41** but not **42** and **43** was previously reported by Dennis *et al* ²⁶

Crotonitrile, obtained commercially as a 1 : 1 mixture of *E* . *Z* isomers **3a** and **3b**, as evident from its ¹H NMR, gave three isolable products (**44**, **45** and **46**). Methyl crotonate regioselectively afforded the diastereoisomeric cycloadducts 1*RS*-(1*R**,5*S**,6*S**,7*S**) and 1*RS*-(1*R**,5*S**,6*R**,7*R**)-6-carbomethoxy-7-methyl-2-oxo-8-phenyl-8-azabi-cyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-ene (**47** and **48**) in the ratio 4 : 5. A single product (**49**) was obtained when methyl vinyl ketone (**39**) was refluxed with the betaine (**35**) in dry THF for 15 h. The lack of any appreciable coupling between H-5 and H-6 confirmed the *exo*-disposition of the ketomethyl group at C-6.

The reaction of 3-oxidopyridinium betaine with electron-deficient alkenes took place regioselectively to furnish two diastereoisomeric cycloadducts. These reactions are controlled largely by the dipole-LUMO-dipolarophile-HOMO interaction with the larger coefficients interacting to give the bicyclo-octene where the electron-deficient group of the dipolarophile occupies the 6-position (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14 Regiocontrol of the cycloaddition of **35** to **36**

References to the published, accepted and communicated papers are given. In addition parts of the work described here and work related to it have been presented as lectures and at a number of conferences²⁸⁻³⁰. These cover the published and as yet unpublished work that we have done.

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